

PROPERTIES OF ADVANCED FIBER COMPOSITES WITH HALLOYSITE NANOTUBE TOUGHENED EPOXY MATRIX

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SUMMARY

Halloysite nanotube (HNT), which is geometrically similar to multi-walled carbon nanotubes, can improve the impact strength of epoxy (EP) substantially. Using HNT toughened EP as matrix, a set of EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites were prepared. The microstructure and mechanical properties of the composites were investigated.

Keywords: halloysite nanotube, epoxy, carbon fiber, interlaminar fracture toughness

INTRODUCTION

Due to its high strength, high modulus and lightweight, carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (EP/CF) composite has found broad applications in structural components for aircraft, high performance automobiles and high speed vessels. However, the weakness of the low strength in the through thickness direction generally leads to interlaminar failures, such as delamination. To improve the interlaminar fracture toughness, a considerable amount of research has been conducted. Examples of the attempts are using Z-pins to connect the laminates, extending fibres through the thickness by weaving, knitting, braiding or stitching [1–5]. However, these techniques are labour intensive and require special fabrication processes which greatly increase the manufacturing cost [4]. Moreover, the complex combination of materials makes it difficult to accurately predict the in-plane mechanical properties, i.e. the tensile, compressive and flexural properties, for a particular stitched composite. For instance, stitching may improve or un-change or even seriously decrease the in-plane properties [1].

Motivated by recent developments in the nanocomposite technology, many researchers attempted to improve the interlaminar properties of fiber reinforced composites using nano-fillers [6–11]. Incorporation of alumina nano-fillers into EP/CF composites resulted in both higher interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and fracture toughness [11]. Gojny et al. [6] found that adding 0.3 wt% double-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTs) into fiber reinforced epoxy composites increased ILSS by 20%. By growing multi-walled CNTs on the surface of SiC fibers, the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IC}) of the hybrid composites was improved by 348% [7]. Siddiqui et al. [9] also gained 60% enhancement on G_{IC} by adding 3 wt% organoclay in epoxy matrix. All these studies

showed a promising path toward the applications of nano-fillers in the fiber reinforced composites. Moreover, the introduction of nano-fillers does not increase the weight of the components made from CF composites.

Halloysite is a fine clay mineral, consisting of tubular particles with multi-layered wall structure. Our previous work [12, 13] has shown that HNTs as low-cost nanotubes can improve the mechanical properties of epoxy significantly. Blending epoxy with 2.3 wt% HNTs increased the Charpy impact strength for 4 times, without sacrificing flexural modulus and strength. The underlying toughening mechanisms were identified as massive micro-cracking, nanotube bridging/pull-out/breaking and main-crack deflection. Given the HNT crack-bridging capability, and considering the low damage resistance of conventional EP/CF composites are largely caused by propagation of internal defects (e.g. microcracks) under external loadings, we used the EP/HNT nanocomposite as matrix in CF composite fabrication in the present study. It was anticipated that the EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites would benefit from the high impact toughness brought in by the HNTs, leading to a new class of CF composites. The microstructure of the EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The mechanical properties and the failure mechanisms of the hybrid composites were studied.

EXPERIMENTS

Preparation of Composite Laminates

The EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites were fabricated from carbon fiber woven fabrics and HNT-filled epoxy by hand lay-up process. Plain woven carbon fibres (TI3101 supplied by Taiwan Electrical Insulators Co.) with a unit weight of 200 g/m² were employed as the reinforcements for the composites. The materials and processing conditions for preparing EP/HNT nanocomposite were essentially the same as reported previously [12]. The nanocomposites were prepared using halloysite (Imerys Tableware New Zealand Limited), EPON Resin 828 (Bisphenol A, Resolution Performance Products) with curing agent 4, 4'-methylene dianiline (MDA, Aldrich) at a 100/27 weight ratio. In summary, a certain amount of halloysite was first dispersed in acetone, and mechanically stirred for half an hour at room temperature. The mixture was then introduced into the epoxy resin and stirred for another 2 hours at 75 °C. After degassing to remove the remaining acetone, MDA was added with gentle mixing for ten minutes. The HNT-filled epoxy was then brushed onto twelve plies of carbon fibre fabrics by hand lay-up process. A 15 µm thick Teflon film was inserted into the mid-plane of the laminates as an initial crack for the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness test. The laminates were finally stacked on an aluminium mould plate and cured in a hot pressing machine (Technical Machine Products Corp.). The curing condition was set as: pre-cure at 80 °C for 2 hours and post-cure at 160 °C for another 4 hours. A low pressure of 0.3MPa was applied for the whole curing process to maintain a laminate thickness of 3.2 ± 0.2 mm. The carbon fiber volume fraction of the composites was 29 ± 1 vol%, determined by combustion of the cured laminates according to ASTM D3171. The halloysite contents varied between 1~5 wt% based on the nanocomposite matrix.

Material Characterization

The morphology of EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites was disclosed using a SEM (JEOL JSM-6700F). The short beam shear (SBS) test (ASTM D 2344) was employed to characterize the apparent interlaminar shear strength of the composites. The SBS specimen of $20.0 \times 6.4 \times 3.2 \text{ mm}^3$ was placed on two cylindrical supports of 3 mm in diameter, and bended by a cylindrical head of 6 mm in diameter at the centre of the specimen until the first failure was recorded. The tests were conducted on a universal testing machine (UTM, MTS Alliance RT/10) with a span/ thickness ratio of 4 and a cross-head rate of 1 mm/min. More than eight specimens for each composite system were tested. To investigate the reinforcing effects of HNTs on ILSS, the cross-sectional area of the damaged samples was examined using a SEM. The flexural modulus and strength of the composites were determined according to ASTM D790 on the same UTM using specimens of $70.0 \times 12.7 \times 3.2 \text{ mm}^3$, cut from the moulded sheet. The specimens were bended with a support span of 50.0 mm at a crosshead speed of 1.3 mm/min. For each composite sample, at least five specimens were tested.

Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IIC}) was evaluated using end-notched flexure (ENF) tests on a hydraulic UTM (MTS 858 Mini Bionix) at a loading rate of 1 mm/min. The specimen length and width (W) were 120 mm and 20 mm, respectively. As shown in Figure 1, the specimen was placed on a three-point bending fixture with a half-span length (L) of 50 mm. The overall Teflon film length was 35 mm and the initial crack length (a_0) was designed to be around 25 mm. For the calculation of G_{IIC} , several methods have been proposed [14], including the analytical compliance method, the direct beam theory and the corrected beam theory [15].

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of specimen geometry for ENF tests.

It was found that no big difference in the toughness values calculated by different methods [16]. The correct beam theory was applied for determining G_{IIC} by Equation (1) in this work.

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9a^2 P_m^2 K}{4mWL^3 H} \quad (1)$$

where m is the slope of the initial straight-line portion of the load-deflection curve. P_m is the maximum load; K is a correction factor for the moment arm and H is a correction factor for the compliance. K and H can be determined by

$$K = 1 - 0.6099(\delta / L)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$H = 1 + 0.3766(\delta / L)^2 \quad (3)$$

where δ is the displacement at the maximum load point. After the ENF tests, the fracture surface of the broken specimens was examined with a SEM.

To minimize the influence of different carbon fibre contents on the mechanical properties, all the mechanical testing results were normalized with carbon fibre volume fraction of 29%. In addition, before all the mechanical tests, all the samples were annealed at 180°C (10°C above T_g) for 2 hours to eliminate residual stress caused by mechanical cutting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphology

The microstructure of EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites was examined by SEM and shown in Figure 2. HNTs were non-uniformly dispersed in the epoxy matrix among carbon fibers. Like in the EP/HNT nanocomposites [12], some HNTs were randomly dispersed in the matrix with large inter-tube distance, while others dispersed in the epoxy with much shorter inter-tube distance, resulting in the formation of HNT-rich regions. Though the HNT-rich regions look like clusters of HNTs, a closer examination of these regions by TEM revealed that the spaces among the HNTs were actually filled by epoxy, refer to our previous work [12]. The HNT-rich regions can be regarded as the rigid composite particles with high content of HNT, which plays an important role in toughening epoxy.

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrographs of EP/HNT/CF composites with 3 wt% HNTs.

Interlaminar Shear Strength

The interlaminar shear strength of the EP/HNT/CF composites with different amount of HNT was listed in Table 1. To eliminate the influence caused by the slight difference in carbon fibre contents and study the effects of HNT concentration, the ILSS was normalized with carbon fibre volume fraction of 29%. As demonstrated by Table 1, with increasing HNT concentration, ILSS of the hybrid composites increased steadily. The improvement on normalized ILSS reached 20% with 5wt% HNT. Similar enhancement was obtained by Wichmann et al. [10] using CNTs, which are much more expensive. Hussain et al. [11] proposed that the addition of nano-sized fillers into epoxy matrix caused higher thermal residual stresses on the fiber surfaces, thus increased the fiber-matrix interface bonding, which led to improved ILSS. To investigate the reinforcing effects of HNTs on the ILSS of our EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites, the damaged area of the composite samples after SBS tests was investigated and shown in Figure-3(a) to Figure-3(f).

Table 1: Interlaminar shear strength of EP/CF composites with different HNT contents.

HNT content in the matrix (wt%)	CF content (vol%)	ILSS (MPa)	Normalized ILSS (MPa)
0	28.4	50.09±1.96	50.79 ±1.99
1	28.7	52.59 ±1.58	53.14 ±1.60
2	28.9	55.06 ±1.46	55.25 ±1.47
3	29.1	60.96±2.64	60.75±2.63
5	29.5	62.52±1.96	61.46±1.93

Figure 3: Typical failure modes in a damaged SBS sample with 3 wt% HNTs: Figure-3(a) the entire view of the damaged zone; Figure-3(b) trans-ply cracking through a HNT-rich particle; (c) enlarged area A in Figure 3(b) showing nanotube bridging in the HNT-rich region; Figure-3(d) matrix microcracking; Figure-3(e) enlarged area B in Figure-3(d) showing nanotube bridging in the epoxy matrix; Figure-3(f) enlarged area C in Figure-3(d) showing a damaged HNT-rich region.

As indicated by Figure-3(a), typical interlaminar shear failure was found; cracks propagated along the fibre–matrix interface or through the carbon fiber plies. The holes were due to the pull out of fibre bundles caused by grinding and ultrasonication in the sample preparation process. Figure-3(b) showed a trans-ply crack passing through a HNT-rich particle, labelled as A. During the trans-laminar crack propagation process, the cracks extended by breaking the HNT-rich particles. A closer investigation of the damaged HNT-rich region revealed that microcracks were generated and stabilized by HNT bridging (Figure-3(c)). The formation and stabilization of microcracks turned the HNT-rich particles into damage zones, which can absorb substantial amount of energy and stop or slow down crack propagation, making the system tougher and stronger. Numerous microcracks were created in the epoxy matrix as shown in Figure-3(d) , but the growth of the microcracks was arrested by HNT bridging (Figure-3(e)) or prevented by the HNT-rich particles (Figure-3(f)). All the above mechanisms contributed to the enhancement of ILSS.

Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

The normalized interlaminar fracture toughness of the fibre composites was shown as a function of halloysite contents in Figure 4. The composites with the EP/HNT matrix have higher fracture toughness than that of the neat epoxy-based fibre composite. By adding only 1wt% HNT, the G_{IIC} increased by 24%. With increasing HNT content to 2wt%, the enhancement upgraded to 37%. It is well known that the fracture toughness of fiber reinforced polymer composites arises mainly from the energy dissipating events, such as fiber-matrix debonding, fiber pull-out and bridging, as well as fracture of matrix and fibers [17]. Given our observation shown in Figure 4, the improvement of G_{IIC} for the EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites in the current study, can be attributed mainly to the increased toughness of the epoxy matrix due to the application of HNT.

Figure 4: Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of composites with different halloysite loadings.

Figure 5 shows the fracture surfaces of the EP/CF composites with and without HNTs after ENF tests. The composite made from neat epoxy (Figure-5(a)) showed sheared

hackle markings in the matrix, which is characteristic of brittle epoxy. The hybrid composite samples containing HNTs presented much rougher matrix surface than those with neat epoxy, resulting from the crack bifurcation and pinning. Moreover, the cracks propagated through breaking the fibres but not along the fibre–matrix interface, as illustrated by Figure-5(b) and Figure-5(c), indicating a strong adhesion between the fiber and the matrix. Meanwhile, the HNT-rich particles nearby carbon fibres were also damaged with nanotube pull-out and formation of microcracks. Figure-5(d) showed debonding between an EP/HNT composite particle and epoxy matrix. Because the HNT-rich particles were tough and strong, they worked like micro-scale fillers in the fracture process. Crack bowing phenomenon with HNT-rich particles can be clearly observed in Figure-5(e). According to the crack bowing theory, the advancing crack is pinned by the particles, causing the crack front to bow out between particles, thus the crack length increases, resulting in higher toughness. From the micrograph in Figure-5(f), it can be seen that several nanotubes bridge a micro-crack with a gap about 200 nm. Due to the nanotube bridging, the micro-cracks were arrested and prevented from developing into large and harmful cracks. Clearly, there are two main factors contributing to the G_{IIC} enhancement. The increased toughness of the epoxy matrix due to incorporation of HNTs is the most important reason for the increased G_{IIC} . On the other hand, a strengthened interfacial adhesion between the carbon fibres and the epoxy matrix due to an unclear mechanism brought in by the nano-tubes makes additional contribution to the higher G_{IIC} .

Figure 5: Fracture surfaces of ENF specimens: Figure-5(a) EP/CF composite without HNT; Figure-5(b) - (f) EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites. (Long arrows indicate the crack propagation direction.)

Flexural Properties

The flexural properties of the EP/CF composites with different halloysite contents were tested. As presented in Figure 6, the flexural modulus and strength increased marginally with the incorporation of HNTs. The slight improvement on the flexural properties should be directly related to the matrix properties which were influenced by the dispersion of HNTs. According to our previous work [12], addition of a few percent of HNTs had little influence on the flexural properties of the EP/HNT nanocomposites; hence changes the flexural properties of the EP/HNT/CF composites insignificantly. Similar results were reported for the organoclay reinforced carbon fibre composites [9].

Figure 6: Flexural properties of EP/CF composites as a function of halloysite content.

CONCLUSION

Halloysite nanotubes were used as nano-fillers in the carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy laminates. The morphological study of the EP/HNT/CF hybrid composites revealed that the HNTs were non-uniformly dispersed in the epoxy matrix, forming a unique microstructure with large number of HNT-rich composite particles enveloped by a

continuous epoxy-rich phase. The effects of HNTs on the mechanical properties of the composites were investigated. An enhancement of 20% in the interlaminar shear strength was obtained with 5wt% HNTs. The delamination fracture resistance under Mode II (shear-type) loading (G_{IIC}) was improved by 37% after introducing 2wt% HNTs into the composites. Little or no effect on the flexural properties was found with various concentrations of HNTs. Mechanism study disclosed that the EP/HNT composite particles acted as typical micro-scale fillers during the fracture of the hybrid composites and impeded the development of crack growth; HNT pull-out and bridging in the damaged HNT-rich particles contributed positively to the interlaminar properties. Meanwhile, the HNTs in the epoxy-rich regions stabilized the microcracks of the matrix by nanotube bridging.

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